

Solution to $x = x + 1$

The equation $x = x + 1$, thought to be impossible has a very simple and elegant solution, \mathfrak{A} , or also known as $\frac{1}{0}$

$$x = x + 1$$

$$x - x = 1$$

Here, we run into a dead end, as $0 \neq 1$. But, instead of taking $x - x$ as 0, we will take it as $0x$

$$0x = 1$$

And finally

$$x = \frac{1}{0}$$

or

$$x = \mathfrak{A}$$

~ by Vedant Wagle